

Income Stream Diversification and Financial Performance of Commercial Banks in Kenya

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Abstract

Banks have resulted in strengthening their portfolio mix by diversifying their portfolios in order to eliminate risks, increase their revenue sources, remain profitable and survive the competitive environment. Diversification being the main challenge encountered by banks aims at minimizing the variability of operations by banks by reducing the concentration of deposits, loans and revenue that is generated from these activities. Income diversification aims at increasing the sources of interest as well as non-interest income, reduce interest rate risk and total unsystematic risk. Capping of rates of interest has been judged to be a threat to performance of the banking institutions in Kenya and thus a need for commercial banking institutions to strengthen by diversification their streams of income. The 43 commercial banking institutions having official license from CBK by December 2017 were the target population of this study. The study analyzed Time Series Cross Sectional unbalanced secondary panel data obtained from KNBS, World Bank website, CBK, published financial accounts statements of all the 43 commercial banking institutions in Kenya, and the Banking survey publications for fifteen years ranging from 2002 to 2017. Four hypotheses were estimated using techniques of Panel data by adoption of fixed effects and random effects. Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) was used to estimate short run model. Income streams diversification had an association that was significantly positive on financial performance of commercial banking institutions in Kenya

Keywords: Portfolio Diversification; Income Streams; Multiple Linear Regressions; Dynamic Panel Model; Fixed Effects

1.0 Introduction

The main essence of management of portfolio and diversification of product in special reference to retail banks is to spread and minimize unsystematic risks associated with banking business, maximize shareholders' wealth, keep the business alive, in the midst of stiffened competitiveness in the industry. The banking system existing in Kenya has progressed over the years as a result of remarkable changes among them depth and breadth of operations, number of institutions as well as ownership structure. These transformations have been a result of challenges posited by deregulation, which occurred in the financial sector, globalization of various banks operations, innovations in the form of technology and adoption of various requirements that are supervisory and prudential leading to conformity with standard internationally. It is important to examine the input-output mix in the portfolio of these banks and the way they have interacted amongst them to determine the individual aggregate performance levels.

The efficient functioning of retail banking institutions that energize capital market deepening is the building block of formation of capital. The Kenyan financial system is considered to be at the top in rank among systems in sub-Saharan Africa (Odhiambo, 2008). Commercial Banking institutions have expanded and registered increased assets. The Kenyan banking system consists of 43 commercial banking institutions and 2 companies for mortgage financing. The commercial banks are grouped into three tiers depending on asset base. Bank performance is connected with how bank managers assemble resources, allocate resources and manage the inherent risks. It could also be seen with regard to quality of assets portfolio, level of liquidity, and net contribution to the development of a nation's economic development.

In comparison with other Economies in East Africa, the banking sector in Kenya has been applauded for its diversification as well as its size. Portfolio allocation is seen to be drifting to favoring assets that are less risky such as liquid cash and government securities. By September 2016, Government securities contribution was at 24% of the sector's balance sheet in comparison to about 18% year average from 2011 to 2015. Private credit to GDP which is the accepted financial development index was estimated at 34.9% in 2015, in comparison to 45% average for countries in Africa Sub-Sahara (CBK, 2016).

1.1 Objectives of the Study

Consequently, the study endeavored to examine the effect of income streams diversification on the financial performance of commercial banking institutions in Kenya.

The study was guided by the following specific objectives:

- i. To examine the effect of interest income on the financial performance of commercial banking institutions in Kenya
- ii. To determine the effect of trading income on the financial performance of commercial banking institutions in Kenya.
- iii. To determine the effect of fees and commissions on the financial performance of commercial banking institutions in Kenya.
- iv. To evaluate the effect of other incomes on the financial performance of commercial banking institutions in Kenya.

1.2 Hypothesis of the Study

The study was based on the following hypothesis:

H₀₁: Interest income has no significant effect on the financial performance of commercial banking institutions in Kenya.

H₀₁: Trading income has no significant effect on the financial performance of commercial banking institutions in Kenya.

H₀₁: Fees and commissions have no significant effect on financial performance of commercial banking institutions in Kenya.

H₀₁: Other incomes have no significant effect on the financial performance of commercial banking institutions in Kenya.

2.0 Theoretical Literature

2.1 Theory of Transaction Cost Economics

Among the dominating perspectives pertaining to scope motivation strategically is provided by transaction cost economics. Firstly it was articulated explicitly by Coase (1937) and subsequently deeply advanced by Williamson (1985), TCE holds that there exist costs of transactions that are linked with what Coase advocated to be “price mechanism,” and Williamson called it as “market governance.” The importance of the notion is the existence of costs linked with transaction negotiation and contracting (transaction costs) incurred on the open market, which is reduced by spearheading these in other respect transactions that are independent beneath the umbrella of a sole corporate entity. There would exist economies of scale that are contractual, for instance, where costs tracked on a single contract would be extended over several transactions. As Coase (1937) inculcated, the possessor or factor of production not necessarily thereof entitled to make rotating contracts

amidst the institution with whom factors being co-operated with, as would be compulsory, certainly, if the abetting were as a result that is direct from the price mechanisms. These series of contracts are substituted ones.

Pertaining to firms that are specifically diversified, Williamson (1975) postulated that the existence of efficiencies with regard to transaction cost that an intramural capital market that is 'miniature' assumes to take control of which capital market externally doesn't. Silverman (1999) went ahead to provide a similar explanation about the reason why firms diversify. The author expounded on properties by a firm for rent generation and concluded that whenever these highly important resources exchange hands via the process of the market, the transaction will accrue contractual hazards that are higher among them license secrecy, loyalties, and problems emanating from learning curve edge. Taking into consideration that these features are important components that explain the returns that are appropriated to an institution, the author highlights that diversification by a firm is a wiser decision to mitigate the severity extent of exposures that surround a contractual alternative from diversification.

The theory recommends at what time the firm should plan newer activities to be around the firm's boundaries and how institutions can be in a position to accrue benefit out of sharing resources among the businesses that are within firm boundaries. It is a theoretical framework that put across the importance of diversification by allowing firms to get market power that is greater by locking out competition through integration vertically in terms of portfolios. Diversified companies are in a position to cross-subsidize their lines of ventures, and lower prices, which assist elevating entry obstacles and/or being able to squeeze competitors completely out of the existing market (Miller, 2009). From the perspective of transaction cost, firms are to diversify whenever in their businesses to expanding the market power as well as organizing the extra activities in a more efficient manner than the current market or their competing firms.

There has been various criticism of TCE approach by several scholars. Moran and Goshal (1996) earmarked TCE assumption to be too weighty and claimed misuse of non-realistic facts could limit the relevance of the theory. The opportunism concept is also deemed to posit too cynical view to human stimulus. Moran and Goshal (1996) stated further that the way used to avoid expediency by close watching and power exercise of control leads to a reduction in performance of employees and henceforth leading to an opposite effect from the intended one. Hill (1990) uses reasoning derived from game-theoretic to assert how the tasks played by expediency are exaggerated in the theory of TCE. Firm in TCE, being categorized as homogenous, forms another basis for criticism. TCE, therefore, gives an explanation of why the firms do exist, but not for their heterogeneous characteristics. TCE henceforth cannot explain the reason institutions classified under the same industry that vary only in their capital funding perform better than the other.

2.2 Empirical Literature

Diversification of income streams can be stated following the work of Ebrahim and Hasan (2008) as the venturing into new earnings in income and generating monetary streams other than normal services of intermediation that are traditional. The study was about the value relevance as a result of the diversification of products of banks that were commercial in the United States. The paper examined variances in the utility relevance derived in bank institution's component of earnings that are interested in nature to activities of noninterest banking, among them fees and commissions, income from trading and income from dividend earned. It studied specifically reactions off the market to variations in revenue of banks from non-interest activities that emanate from extension into innovative financial services lines apart from traditional intermediation activities. A sample from the commercial banks was studied for duration between the years 1993 and 2002. Analysis from the study showed that returns annually that are abnormal have a positive and significant association with variations in the segment of bank earnings that is noninterest in comparison with changes in the segment of earnings that is from interest. The trend for smaller banks is obvious and preceding

the year 1999, whereby act by Gramm-Leach-Bliley permitted venturing by commercial banks into more noninterest activities of banking. The study acts as an extension of a long research of accounting standoff in derived value relevance of earnings as an application to components of bank earnings.

In the Kenyan context, Kiweu (2012) study sought to establish how the concentration of revenue versus diversification influences banking institutions' financial performance. The study examined how income diversification affects commercial banks' earnings, for it is assumed that it can minimize volatility and inherent risk. The assessment focus was on commercial banking institutions' primary income sources of non-interest, among them fees and commissions, trading income and interest earnings. HHI diversification index was used to compute income stream diversification while ROA, ROE and risk-adjusted returns were used to measure financial performance. The information discovered from the study highlighted little benefits if after all there existed any to be anticipated from income diversity away from the traditional and normal banking activities however it also revealed benefits of growing non-interest incomes during the duration of inquiry ranging from the year 2000 and 2010. The enquiry also was successful in establishing that top tier banks tend to adopt more diversity as opposed to low tier banks and generates higher returns.

Teimet, Ochieng and Anywa (2011) investigated the diversification of the sources of income and commercial banking institutions' financial performance. In their investigation, HHI was used to enable analyze diversification and concentration. The design employed in this research was a longitudinal approach. Five years of trends of income streams pertaining to all commercial banking institutions in Kenya were studied. This investigation upheld that top tier commercial banks are more diversified than small tier ones. The investigation, on the contrary, found that the level of diversification has a significantly positive impact on Kenyan commercial banking financial performance and the two main avenues of revenue, which are non-interest and interest are positively associated.

Sanya and Wolfe (2011) scrutinized the diversification effect of revenue on banking institutions' performance and risk in the context of economies that are emerging. The results showed that diversification reduces the risk of insolvency and enhancement of profitability of banks. The enquiry undertook a dataset, which was a panel consisting of 226 commercial banks that were listed across eleven economies that are emerging. A new approach of methodology, System GMM estimators, was used and what was found in the study empirically provided evidence on the dexterities of a shift observed in the direction of activities generating non-interest revenue on the risk of insolvency and performance by banks. The most important finding was that diversification around the two activities for generating income from interest as well as income classified as non-interest reduces risk of insolvency and henceforth profitability is enhanced. As per the findings, these advantages are sizeable for banks with modest risk vulnerabilities and that are bigger. These results by extension to stakeholders have significant shrewd implications. The stakeholders include managers of banks, supervisory regulators and those who have a common interest and direct benefit in promoting bank performance and stability.

Gambacorta, Scatigna, and Yang (2014), using a nonlinear approach did a study on the diversity and earnings of banking institutions. Information from ninety-eight active international banks with their headquarters in twenty-seven countries over the period 1994 to 2012 was targeted. The design employed in the study was descriptive. The link between the diversification of income stated ratio of noninterest earnings to the total earnings and nonlinear ROA of banks was analyzed. The most important result found indicated the existence of correlation, which is positive between streams of income diversity and banking institutions' profitability but to a certain degree, which is 30% of the ratio of diversity. Diversification advantages for global systemically important banks (GSIBs) are small in size but are significantly more so when we use returns that are volatility-adjusted to be a measure of the profitability of banks.

Doumpos, Gaganis, and Pasiouras, (2013), studied diversification of banks and overall financial strength, which was a shred of international evidence around the crisis. The study used an indicator of rigorous overall financial strength, which was founded along CAMEL framework dimensions. The study examined the relationship that exists between on-and-off balance sheet diversity, income diversity and earning assets diversity on banks' overall financial strength. Diversification of income was found to be of more importance to banks domiciled in countries that are least developed as compared to the banks in more advanced economies. However, it was concluded the contrary concerning diversity amongst on and off-balance sheet activities. The discovery divulged that diversification of earning assets, as well as of income could lessen the negative impact of the monetary difficulty on bank achievement of financial soundness. A positively significant association was prevailing on diversification and overall financial strength, which was found to exist after nesting effects, endogeneity and self-selection having been accounted for, and having used a varying way for setting up the indicator of financial strength.

Elsas, Hackethal, Holzhauser, (2010), did a research study on the structure of banking institutions' diversification, which was issued in the publication of banking and finance. The study used a quantitative research design and panel data collected from nine countries for the duration of eight years from 1996 to 2003. The study tested how diversification of revenue simultaneously with expanding the size of bank impacts the value of banks. Employing a framework that is comprehensive for bank performance quantification, the study findings were that there is an absence of evidence for discounts that are conglomerate, unlike research studies concentrating on industrial firms. Diversification of revenue that includes fees and commissions, trading income, rental income, and other incomes contributes positively to the profitability of bank and is connected with a soaring valuation of the market. This effect on financial performance does not necessarily depend on whether diversification was reached by means of organic growth. The results of the study thus recommend further studies to be done on the anatomy of bank diversification.

A research study was done by Calmes and Theore, (2013) was on diversification, the product mix of banks change and performance where the multivariate GARCH was applied to bank data in Canada. The study period under which the study was conducted was between the years 1997 and 2010. Some key volatility that is conditional revealed these benefits might be varied over the various cycles of business as well as through time. A new composition with a basis on the multivariate GARCH methodology and an adjusted Hausman test was used. The main finding suggested that the composition of income from non-interest activities produce diversification gains that are ineligible as opposed to business lines of banks that are traditional. Diversification normally works for the composition that is related more to banking and as well market-oriented, which is capital market fees and trading income. During crisis episodes, not surprising even though these benefits derived from diversification seem to fade for a majority of the components, other than for securitization and insurance since they act as buffers. The study suggested a conclusion consistent with the literature, despite the coming into being of the model of business of banking, fees and commission related to activities that are traditional to banks that includes credit card, deposit and loan fees. They are the most steady and profitable income streams. Ideally, this engages the shift from heavily relying on income from interest streams linked with activities of intermediation in traditional mechanisms to innovative alternative activities that earn income from non-interest streams.

Olweny and ship's (2010) study was to evaluate and determine bank-specific factors, which include operational cost efficiency, capital adequacy, quality of assets, liquidity, and diversification of income effects and the banks' profitability in the context of the Kenyan market. The additional intent was to evaluate the influence of factors of market structure, market concentration and foreign ownership, on the Kenyan commercial banks' performance measured by various indicators of profitability. This research study adopted the design of panel data using explanatory approach to undertake the study objectives. Yearly financial statements and published reports of thirty-eight banks identified as commercial in Kenya from the year 2002 to 2008 were derived from

the CBK and survey report of banks. The financial data was examined using the technique of multiple linear regressions. Survey data outcome indicated that every factor that was bank-specific exhibited an impact deemed quantitatively significant on profitability, while it was observed an insignificant effect on the market factors. The study basing on its findings recommended policies that would stimulate diversification of revenue, operational costs reduction, decrease risk from credit and motivate banks to decrease their holdings in liquidity. Further research on determinants that impact commercial banks' liquidity in the Kenyan context could be of value addition to the banking institutions' financial performance and scholarly literature.

3.0 Research Methodology

The design adopted by the researcher was correlational and data in secondary form was gathered from financial statements published annually by commercial banking institutions in Kenya. Panel data collected were subjected to analysis by employing descriptive statistics, regression and correlation analysis. Study findings are presented in form of tabulations and figures.

A general Panel regression model accommodating all the hypotheses that explain income streams diversification and the independent variables obtained therefrom, the study can, therefore, be adopted following the work of Berger et al., (2010). The model is dependent on the calculated values of ROA, ROE and various income streams as independent variables of each bank for the period 2002-2017.

$$ROE_{i,t} = f(\text{INT}, \text{NTI}, \text{FC}, \text{OIC}) \quad (3.6a)$$

$$ROA_{i,t} = f(\text{INT}, \text{NTI}, \text{FC}, \text{OIC}) \quad (3.6b)$$

Upon linearization and parametrization which involved transforming the variables into natural logarithms the long run model was specified as:

$$ROE_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{INT}_{i,t} + \beta_2 \text{NTI}_{i,t} + \beta_3 \text{FC}_{i,t} + \beta_4 \text{OIC}_{i,t} + \alpha_i + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (3.6c)$$

$$ROA_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{INT}_{i,t} + \beta_2 \text{NTI}_{i,t} + \beta_3 \text{FC}_{i,t} + \beta_4 \text{OIC}_{i,t} + \alpha_i + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (3.6d)$$

And the specification of the short run model was:

$$ROE_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \lambda \text{ROE}_{i,t-1} + \beta_1 \text{INT}_{i,t} + \beta_2 \text{NTI}_{i,t} + \beta_3 \text{FC}_{i,t} + \beta_4 \text{OIC}_{i,t} + \alpha_i + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (3.6e)$$

$$ROA_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \lambda \text{ROE}_{i,t-1} + \beta_1 \text{INT}_{i,t} + \beta_2 \text{NTI}_{i,t} + \beta_3 \text{FC}_{i,t} + \beta_4 \text{OIC}_{i,t} + \alpha_i + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (3.6f)$$

where INT, NTI, FC, OIC are interest income, net trading income, fees and commissions, other income respectively for Bank i at time t .

4.0 Findings and Discussion

4.1 Descriptive Statistics for Income Streams Diversification

Descriptive statistics adopted in this assessment included measures of central tendency and dispersion. The former had mean and median and the later had a standard deviation, minimum, maximum, skewness and kurtosis. Normality was examined through use of Jarque-Bera test. The intent of the assessment was to examine the association of income streams diversification and Kenyan commercial banking institutions' financial performance. This diversification was operationalized as interest income, trading income, fees and commission and other income streams. As tabulated in Table 4.1, the average interest income was 9.75, with minimum of 2 maximum of 31.52. The average trading income was 7.73, with minimum of 2.01 and maximum of 28.89. Fees

and commissions averaged at 8.42, with standard deviation of 5.79. Other income averaged at 7.42 which had the least average and minimum of 1.10. None of income streams diversification had the Jarque-Berra coefficient greater than 0.05. Hence all were not normally distributed.

Table 4.1 Descriptive Statistics for Income Streams Diversification

	Interest income	Trading income	Fees & commission	Other income
Mean	9.75	7.73	8.42	7.42
Median	7.59	5.86	6.05	5.69
Maximum	31.52	28.89	29.76	29.62
Minimum	2.00	2.01	2.07	1.10
Std. Dev.	3.39	5.02	5.79	6.12
Skewness	3.11	0.91	1.35	1.19
Kurtosis	19.22	2.97	4.11	3.79
Jarque-Bera	7220.68	78.93	204.55	150.92
Probability	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Sum	4450.96	4438.16	4830.25	4835.74
Sum Sq. Dev.	6591.90	14454.06	19230.93	21433.09
Observations	574	574	574	574

4.2 Panel Unit Roots for Income Streams Diversification

Stationarity was examined using Levin, Lin and Chu, Im, Pesaran and Shi-W, ADF and Philips Perrons. The null hypothesis for these tests stated that the data was not stationary against an alternative that the data was stationary. As tabulated in Table 4.2, the null hypothesis stated that attributes of income services diversification were not stationary against an alternative that they were stationary. Study findings documented that adequate evidence existed to support nonacceptance of the null hypothesis and interpretation that interest income, trading income, fees and commission and other income were stationary and thus no need to lag them prior to fitting regression models against commercial banks' performance. These findings differed with Ochieng, Olweny, Oluoch and Ochere (2019a), who found that gross portfolio flows and volatility of stock markets in Kenya were stationary at first difference.

Table 4.2 Panel Unit Roots for Income Streams Diversification

Variable	Method	Statistic	Prob.
Interest income	Levin, Lin & Chu t*	-6.0691	0.0000
	Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat	-3.4883	0.0002
	ADF - Fisher Chi-square	131.1780	0.0001
	PP - Fisher Chi-square	214.5250	0.0000
Trading income	Levin, Lin & Chu t*	-10.4830	0.0000
	Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat	-6.7637	0.0000
	ADF - Fisher Chi-square	194.4140	0.0000
	PP - Fisher Chi-square	280.2960	0.0000
Fees and commission	Levin, Lin & Chu t*	-6.1078	0.0000
	Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat	-4.6693	0.0000
	ADF - Fisher Chi-square	142.7940	0.0000
	PP - Fisher Chi-square	228.2800	0.0000
Other income	Levin, Lin & Chu t*	-7.2003	0.0000
	Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat	-4.8380	0.0000
	ADF - Fisher Chi-square	150.2580	0.0000
	PP - Fisher Chi-square	239.7090	0.0000

4.3 Multicollinearity Test for Income Streams Diversification

Classical regression modelling is anchored on the assumption that there is no collinearity amongst independent variables. Multicollinearity was scrutinized by utilization of variance inflation factors and tolerance limits. The cut-off rule was that there is no collinearity if VIF was less than 10 or tolerance limits superseded 0.1. This was in line with (Baltagi, 2005). The outcome indicated in Table 4.3, revealed that there was no collinearity amongst interest income, trading income, fees and commission and other income when they were predicting ROE and ROA. Consequently, they were jointly fitted in the model to scrutinize the association of income streams diversification on banking institutions' performance in Kenya.

Table 4.3 Multicollinearity Test for Income Streams Diversification

Dependent Variable		Collinearity Statistics	
		Tolerance	VIF
ROE	Interest Income	0.822	1.217
	Trading income	0.645	1.549
	Fees and Commission	0.373	2.679
	Other Income	0.4	2.501
ROA	Interest Income	0.822	1.217
	Trading income	0.645	1.549
	Fees and Commission	0.373	2.679
	Other Income	0.4	2.501

4.4 Correlation Analysis of Income Streams Diversification

Pearson correlation coefficient was adopted to scrutinize the strength of the association of income streams diversification and banking performance in Kenya. It was selected since all variables were in the same scale. As tabulated in Table 4.4, study findings disclosed significantly positive association of interest income streams, trading income stream, fees and commissions stream and other streams of income on ROE ($\rho = 0.532, 0.645, 0.728, 0.708$, p value <0.0) and ROA ($\rho = 0.456, 0.447, 0.506, 0.488$, p value <0.05). These findings mirrored Ebrahim and Hasan (2008), who reported positively significant interrelation of income diversification and banking performance. Also, they agreed with Kiweu (2012), who found significant contribution of income streams diversification and banking performance in Kenya.

Table 4.4 Correlation Analysis of Income Streams Diversification

		ROE	ROA	Interest Income	Trading income	Fees & Commission	Other Income
ROE	Pearson Correlation	1					
ROA	Pearson Correlation	.787**	1				
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000					
	N	574	574				
Interest Income	Pearson Correlation	.532**	.456**	1			
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000				
	N	574	574	574			
Trading income	Pearson Correlation	.645**	.447**	.368**	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000			
	N	574	574	574	574		
Fees & Commission	Pearson Correlation	.728**	.506**	.370**	.555**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000		
	N	574	574	574	574	574	
Other Income	Pearson Correlation	.703**	.488**	.341**	.516**	.566**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	
	N	574	574	574	574	574	574

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

4.5 Panel Heteroskedasticity Test for Income Streams Diversification

Study findings as tabulated in Table 4.5, disclosed that there was enough corroboration to justify nonacceptance of the null hypothesis and infer that there was no uniformity of variance across the error terms and the most proper model to fit was fixed generalized least squares model or fit a regression model with robust standard errors. Hence, models of regressions containing robust standard errors were deployed in the assessment to scrutinize the association of income streams diversifications and banking performance in Kenya.

Table 4.5 Panel Heteroskedasticity Test for Income Streams Diversification of Commercial Banks in Kenya

Dependent Variable	Chi Square	P value
ROE	2324.79	0.000
ROA	4219.76	0.000

4.6 Panel Serial Autocorrelation Test for Income Streams Diversification

Study outcome, as tabulated in Table 4.6, disclosed the existence of enough corroboration to justify nonacceptance of the null hypothesis and infer that non-existence of serial correlation across the error terms and the most proper model to fit was fixed generalized least squares model or fit regression model with robust standard errors. Hence, models of regressions containing robust standard errors were deployed in the assessment to scrutinize the association of income streams diversifications and banking performance in Kenya.

Table 4.6 Panel Serial Autocorrelation Test for Income Streams Diversification of Commercial Banks in Kenya

Dependent Variable	Chi Square	P value
ROE	75.62	0.000
ROA	79.65	0.000

4.7 Panel Granger Causality Test for Income Streams Diversification

Study outcome as tabulated in Table 4.7, there was unidirectional causality from interest income to ROE, trading income to ROE, fees and commission to ROE, other income to ROE. Also, there was unidirectional causality from interest income, trading income, fees and commission and other income to ROA. There was bidirectional causality from trading income to interest income and other income to fees and commission.

Table 4.7 Panel Granger Causality Test for Income Streams Diversification

Null Hypothesis:	F-Statistic	Prob	Conclusion
ROA does not Granger Cause ROE	1.919	0.148	
ROE does not Granger Cause ROA	1.578	0.207	No causality
Interest income does not Granger Cause ROE	0.080	0.923	
ROE does not Granger Cause interest income	12.449	0.000	Unidirectional
Trading income does not Granger Cause ROE	0.549	0.578	
ROE does not Granger Cause trading income	30.336	0.000	Unidirectional
Fees and commission does not Granger Cause ROE	0.156	0.856	
ROE does not Granger Cause fees and commission	19.754	0.000	Unidirectional
Other income does not Granger Cause ROE	0.062	0.940	
ROE does not Granger Cause other income	17.537	0.000	Unidirectional
Interest income does not Granger Cause ROA	0.852	0.427	
ROA does not Granger Cause interest income	11.274	0.000	Unidirectional
Trading income does not Granger Cause ROA	0.275	0.760	
ROA does not Granger Cause trading income	10.905	0.000	Unidirectional
Fees commission does not Granger Cause ROA	0.030	0.971	
ROA does not Granger Cause fees commission	7.020	0.001	Unidirectional
Other income does not Granger Cause ROA	0.334	0.716	
ROA does not Granger Cause other income	7.002	0.001	Unidirectional

Trading income does not Granger Cause interest income	6.166	0.002	
Interest income does not Granger Cause trading income	4.078	0.018	Bidirectional
Fees and commission does not Granger Cause interest income	10.900	0.000	Unidirectional
Interest income does not Granger Cause fees and commission	1.211	0.299	
Other income does not Granger Cause interest income	11.934	0.000	Unidirectional
Interest income does not Granger Cause other income	1.568	0.210	
Fees and commission does not Granger Cause trading income	9.365	0.000	Unidirectional
Trading income does not Granger Cause fees and commission	1.097	0.335	
Other income does not Granger Cause trading income	10.560	0.000	Unidirectional
Trading income does not Granger Cause other income	2.220	0.110	
Other income does not Granger Cause fees and commission	8.702	0.000	Bidirectional
Fees and commission does not Granger Cause other income	3.330	0.037	

4.8 Panel Hausman Test for Income Streams Diversification

Study outcome as tabulated in Table 4.8, the p value was 0.000 which was smaller than 0.05. This meant enough justification for non-acceptance of the null hypothesis and deducing that the most appropriate model to fit was fixed effects. Hence, fixed effects were employed to scrutinize association of income streams diversification and ROE and ROA of banks in the context of Kenya

Table 4.8 Panel Hausman Test for Income Streams Diversification

Dependent	Test Summary		Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
ROE			31.597	4	0.000
	Variable	Fixed	Random	Var (Diff.)	Prob.
	Interest income	0.786	0.877	0.001	0.015
	Trading income	0.493	0.547	0.000	0.000
	Fees & commission	0.626	0.657	0.000	0.019
	Other income	0.464	0.515	0.000	0.001
ROA			9.247	4	0.05
	Variable	Fixed	Random	Var (Diff.)	Prob.
	Interest income	0.186	0.202	0.000	0.059
	Trading income	0.048	0.054	0.000	0.020
	Fees & commission	0.100	0.103	0.000	0.333
	Other income	0.066	0.071	0.000	0.129

4.9 Hypothesis Testing

As shown in Table 4.9, there was significant association of income streams and ROE of commercial banking institutions in Kenya ($F= 56.9384$, p value <0.05). The coefficient of determination of 0.8183 indicated that 81.83 percent of changes in ROE was accounted for by interest income, trading income, fees and commission and other income streams. The remainder was accounted for by other attributes kept out from the model. Interest income had positively significant effect on ROE ($\beta = 0.7865$, p value <0.05). This indicates that unit increase in interest income increased ROE by 0.7865 while holding interest income, trading income, fees and commission and other income constant. Secondly, trading income had significant positive effect on ROE ($\beta=0.4932$, p value <0.05). This denotes that unit increase in trading income increased ROE by 0.4932 while holding constant interest income, fees and commission and other income constant. Thirdly, fees and commission had positive and significant effect on ROE ($\beta=0.6263$, p value <0.05). This indicated that unit increase in fees and commission increases ROE by 0.6263 units while holding interest income, trading income and other income constant. Finally, there was positive and significant effect of other income on ROE

($\beta=0.4644$, p value <0.05). This denotes that unit increase in other income increased ROE by .4644 while holding constant interest income, trading income and fees and commission.

$$ROE = -2.8243 + 0.7865 * \text{Interest income} + 0.4932 * \text{Trading income} + 0.6263 * \text{Fees and Commission} + 0.4644 * \text{Other income} \dots\dots\dots 4.1$$

Table 4.9 Fixed Effects on Effect of Income Streams Diversification on ROE

Variable	Coefficient	Robust Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-2.8243	1.0350	-2.7288	0.0066
Interest income	0.7865	0.1170	6.7241	0.0000
Trading income	0.4932	0.0743	6.6371	0.0000
Fees and commission	0.6263	0.0831	7.5350	0.0000
Other income	0.4644	0.0786	5.9090	0.0000
R-squared	0.8183	Mean dependent var		16.2697
Adjusted R-squared	0.8039	S.D. dependent var		14.7145
S.E. of regression	6.5156	Akaike info criterion		6.6582
Sum squared residuals	22542.4100	Schwarz criterion		6.9843
Log likelihood	-1867.9110	Hannan-Quinn criterion.		6.7854
F-statistic	56.9384	Durbin-Watson stat		1.4481
Prob(F-statistic)	0.0000			

As shown in Table 4.10, there was significant effect of income streams on ROA of commercial banks in Kenya ($F= 40.2951$, p value <0.05). The coefficient of determination of 0.2207, indicated that 22.07 percent of changes in ROA was accounted for by interest income, trading income, fees and commission and other income streams. The remainder was accounted for by other attributes excluded from the model. Interest income had positive significant effect on ROA ($\beta = 0.2017$, p value <0.05). This indicates that unit increase in interest income increased ROE by 0.2017 while holding interest income, trading income, fees and commission and other income constant. Secondly, trading income had significant positive effect on ROA ($\beta=0.0545$, p value <0.05). This implies that unit increase in trading income increased ROA by 0.0545 while holding constant interest income, fees and commission and other income constant. Thirdly, fees and commission had positive and significant effect on ROA ($\beta=0.1028$, p value <0.05). This indicated that unit increase in fees and commission increases ROA by 0.1028 units while holding interest income, trading income and other income constant. Finally, there was positive and significant effect of other income on ROA ($\beta=0.0708$, p value <0.05). This implies that unit increase in other income increased ROA by 0.0708 while holding constant interest income, trading income and fees and commission.

$$ROA = -1.4455 + 0.2017 * \text{Interest income} + 0.0545 * \text{Trading income} + 0.1028 * \text{Fees and Commission} + 0.0708 * \text{Other income} \dots\dots\dots 4.2$$

Table 4.10 Random Effects on Effect of Income Streams Diversification ROA

Variable	Coefficient	Robust Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-1.4455	0.4335	-3.3347	0.0009
Interest income	0.2017	0.0353	5.7068	0.0000
Trading income	0.0545	0.0229	2.3775	0.0178
Fees and commission	0.1028	0.0257	4.0041	0.0001
Other income	0.0708	0.0242	2.9304	0.0035
R-squared	0.2207	Mean dependent var		0.5318
Adjusted R-squared	0.2153	S.D. dependent var		2.2944
S.E. of regression	2.0330	Sum squared residuals		2351.8350

F-statistic	40.2951	Durbin-Watson stat	0.8269
Prob(F-statistic)	0.0000		

Dynamic panel modelling was adopted to examine short run effects on the effect of income streams diversification on the financial performance of commercial banking institutions in Kenya. As tabulated in Table 4.11, there was significant effect of income streams diversification on financial performance of commercial banks in Kenya (Wald Chi square = 380.90, p value < 0.05). There was positive and significant effect of lagged return on equity, interest income, trading income, fees and commission and other incomes.

$$ROE = -1.7024 + 0.1477*ROE_{t-1} + 0.5778*Interest\ income + 0.4104 * Trading\ income + 0.5411 * Fees\ and\ Commission + 0.4047*Other\ income \dots\dots\dots 4.3$$

Table 4.11 Dynamic Panel Model on Effect of Income Streams Diversification on ROE

```

Arellano-Bond dynamic panel-data estimation Number of obs      =      495
Group variable: id                          Number of groups     =      39
Time variable: year

Obs per group:  min =      7
                  avg = 12.69231
                  max =     14

Number of instruments =    110          Wald chi2(5)         =    380.90
                                          Prob > chi2          =    0.0000
    
```

One-step results

	Coef.	Std. Err.	z	P> z	[95% Conf. Interval]	
roe						
L1.	.1477377	.0476915	3.10	0.002	.0542641	.2412113
interest_income	.577765	.1256555	4.60	0.000	.3314848	.8240452
trading_income	.4104997	.0761901	5.39	0.000	.2611699	.5598294
fees_commission	.541079	.0868685	6.23	0.000	.3708199	.7113381
other_income	.4047023	.0809904	5.00	0.000	.2459639	.5634406
_cons	-1.702351	1.219365	-1.40	0.163	-4.092262	.6875594

Sargan test was adopted to examine the possibilities of the model underestimation. The null hypothesis stated that underlying conditions for the model were satisfied against an alternative of their non-satisfaction. Findings shown in Table 4.50 revealed that the model was correctly identified since its p value was less than 0.05.

Table 4.12 Sargan Test for Model

```

Sargan test of overidentifying restrictions
H0: overidentifying restrictions are valid

chi2(104) = 162.2197
Prob > chi2 = 0.0002
    
```

As shown in Table 4.13, there was a significant effect of income streams diversification on financial performance of commercial banks in Kenya (Wald Chi square = 206.55, p value < 0.05). There was positive

and significant effect of lagged return on assets, interest income, trading income, fees and commission and other incomes and return on assets

$$ROA = -1.1459 + 0.5283*ROA_{t-1} + 0.0771*Interest\ income + 0.0640 * Trading\ income + 0.0742 * Fees\ and\ Commission + 0.0424*Other\ income \dots\dots\dots 4.4$$

Table 4.13 Dynamic Panel Model on Effect of Income Streams Diversification on ROA

```

Arellano-Bond dynamic panel-data estimation  Number of obs      =      495
Group variable: id                          Number of groups     =      39
Time variable: year

Obs per group:  min =      7
                  avg = 12.69231
                  max =     14

Number of instruments = 110                  Wald chi2(5)         =    206.55
                                                Prob > chi2          =    0.0000
    
```

One-step results

roa	Coef.	Std. Err.	z	P> z	[95% Conf. Interval]	
roa						
L1.	.5283636	.0476834	11.08	0.000	.4349058	.6218214
interest_income	.077054	.0376624	2.05	0.041	.0032372	.1508709
trading_income	.063961	.0224301	2.85	0.004	.0199988	.1079231
fees_commission	.074157	.0255842	2.90	0.004	.0240128	.1243011
other_income	.0423893	.024113	1.76	0.079	-.0048714	.08965
_cons	-1.145908	.3346126	-3.42	0.001	-1.801737	-.4900797

Instruments for differenced equation

Sargan test was adopted to examine the possibilities of the model underestimation. The null hypothesis stated that underlying conditions for the model were satisfied against an alternative of their non-satisfaction. Findings shown in Table 4.51 revealed that the model was correctly identified since its p value was less than 0.05.

Table 4.14 Sargan Test for Model

Sargan test of overidentifying restrictions

H0: overidentifying restrictions are valid

chi2(104) = 237.8499

Prob > chi2 = 0.0000

Conclusions and Recommendations

The intent of the study was to scrutinize the effect of income streams diversification on the financial performance of commercial banking institutions in Kenya. The most common stream of income amongst commercial banks was interest income, followed by fees and commission and trading income. There was disclosure of positively significant association by analysis of correlation positive on the effect of interest income, trading income and fees and income and banking performance. Static regression modelling disclosed

positive and significant effect of interest income, trading income, fees and commission and return on assets and returned on equity, respectively.

Modeling using dynamic panel regression revealed a positive and significant effect of past return on equity, interest income, trading income and fees and commission on return on equity. Also, there was positive and significant effect of past return of assets, interest income, trading income and fees and commission and return on assets of commercial banks in Kenya.

Commercial banking institutions should diversify the generation of income instead of reliance on income services. This would minimize possibilities of financial loss amongst commercial banks and financial institutions. Measures to maintain financial soundness of commercial banks should be developed and this would eliminate possibilities of bank panics and banks run amongst financial stakeholders.

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